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KNOWING THE END TO TRANSFORM THE BEGINNING

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ABSTRACT:

This poster seeks to create a pedagogical program aimed at students from public and private schools, where SEAP-RJ, through criminal police officers trained and qualified with Non-Violent Communication techniques, crime prevention, violence prevention due to intolerance of gender, race, color among others.